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International Scientific Co-publications in Italian Regions

International scientific co-publications in the Italian regions have increased by an average of 44.85% between 2018 and 2023. Eurostat calculates international scientific co-publications, defined as the number of scientific publications with at least one co-author based abroad. Abroad refers to a non-EU country. The source for this analysis is Scopus. The analyzed data refers to the 20 Italian regions during the period from 2018 to 2023.

Trend of International Scientific Co-publications in Italian Regions in 2023. The data for 2023 sheds light on a research landscape in Italy characterized by impressive variety and significant regional disparities. The leadership of Friuli Venezia Giulia with a score of 316 demonstrates not only the existence of a robust research ecosystem in the region but also a strong inclination towards international collaboration, a fundamental element in an era where science and technology transcend national borders. Similarly, Trentino Alto Adige and Lazio, with scores of 293 and 255 respectively, reflect a dynamic scientific environment open to international exchange and collaboration, likely favored by the strong presence of prominent research institutes and universities. On the other hand, the position of Valle d'Aosta, with the lowest score of 49, highlights the challenges faced by small regions in entering broader research networks, potentially due to limitations in resources, infrastructure, or critical mass of researchers. This suggests the need for targeted policies to support scientific research and international collaboration even in these areas, to avoid leaving them behind in the advancement of global knowledge. It is interesting to note how regions with industrial and academic backgrounds, such as Emilia Romagna and Lombardy, have high scores, albeit not at the top, suggesting that the ability to produce quality research and establish significant collaborations is well distributed throughout the country, but with room for improvement in the intensity and breadth of international collaborations. Additionally, regions like Tuscany and Liguria, with scores of 238 and 229 respectively, demonstrate that areas with a strong cultural and tourist tradition can also be centers of excellence in research and innovation, underscoring the importance of a holistic approach to regional development that integrates different sectors.

Trend of International Scientific Co-publications in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. The data on international scientific co-publications in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023 shows a general positive trend towards greater international collaboration in research. All regions have recorded an increase in both absolute and percentage terms, demonstrating a growing commitment to actively contributing to and participating in the global scientific community. The absolute variation in data shows a heterogeneous trend among the regions, with Abruzzo showing the largest absolute increase (76.1758) and Basilicata the smallest (13.83812), suggesting a diversity of dynamics and research development capacities at the regional level. From a percentage perspective, Marche stands out with an impressive increase of 82.908%, indicating significant potential for growth and development in international collaborative research. Regions like Puglia and Campania also show percentage

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increases of over 60%, highlighting how the South is improving its presence in global research. Conversely, Basilicata, despite the modest absolute increase, has nonetheless recorded a percentage growth of 18.541%, highlighting how each region is contributing to scientific progress, albeit at different rates. These data reflect not only the importance of international collaboration in scientific research but also how this trend is distributed heterogeneously across Italy. The growth in international scientific co-publications indicates a growing alignment with global research standards and a strengthening of scientific networks that transcend national borders. However, the variety of percentage variations also suggests the importance of differentiated support policies that take into account regional specificities to further enhance the country's research and innovation capacity as a whole.

Italian Macro-regions. The evolution of international scientific co-publications among the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2023 provides an illustrative overview of the country's research orientation towards greater integration and international collaboration. This upward trend, evident in all macro-regions, from North to South, through the Center, highlights not only a commitment to scientific excellence but also a recognition of the crucial importance of global synergies in research. Specifically, Central Italy stands out for its notable qualitative leap, with an increase from 139 to 204. This progression can be attributed to the presence of a highly stimulating and competitive environment, characterized by world-class universities, excellence research institutes, and a vibrant academic community that attract international collaborations. These factors create a fertile ground for cutting-edge research that often results in joint publications with foreign partners, demonstrating the effectiveness of policies encouraging research and international cooperation. Northern Italy, with an initially parallel trend to the Center, shows an evolution from 139.65 to 194.73. The solidity of this increase reflects the presence of advanced industrial and technological hubs, where applied research meets the production world, facilitating exchanges and joint projects with international entities. The extensive network of collaborations established by universities and research centers in the North facilitates access to European and international funding, further promoting joint scientific production. The South, although starting from more modest numbers, shows a growth trend from 85.65 to 130.54, highlighting an increasing openness towards the internationalization of research. This progression, although slower than in the Center and North, is particularly significant, indicating a gradual overcoming of structural barriers and an increase in scientific skills and infrastructures. Initiatives aimed at improving research quality and encouraging participation in international networks are beginning to bear fruit, contributing to greater recognition of the research produced in the South.

North-South Divide. The analysis of international scientific co-publications in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 highlights the existence of a North-South divide. Although all macro-regions have shown a positive trend and growth in the number of joint publications at the international level, the North and Central Italy start from higher bases and maintain constant growth rates, reflecting greater integration into global research networks and a consolidated scientific infrastructure. The South, while recording significant increases and showing a growing openness towards international collaboration, starts from significantly lower numbers, underscoring the persistent challenges in terms of access to resources, funding, and international networking opportunities. This gap between North and South not only reflects existing disparities in investment in research and development and support infrastructures for science but also indicates the need for targeted policies to promote excellence and innovation in all regions, in order to bridge this divide and fully exploit Italy's scientific potential on a global scale.

Economic Policies to Promote International Scientific Co-publications. To stimulate an increase in international scientific co-publications in Italian regions, it would be essential to implement economic

policies aimed at strengthening international collaboration and innovation. An effective approach could include allocating greater funds for research and development, with particular emphasis on projects that promote cooperation between Italian and foreign research institutes. Specific financial incentives, such as scholarships for researcher and doctoral student mobility, could facilitate exchanges of knowledge and skills. Additionally, support for excellence networks involving universities, research centers, and industries can create stable platforms for international collaboration. Policies should also encourage public-private partnerships, leveraging European funding for projects that require a transnational approach. Finally, it is crucial to improve the digital and technological infrastructures of academic institutions, enabling researchers to network more efficiently with their international colleagues. These measures, accompanied by simplified bureaucracy and solid intellectual property support, can significantly increase the number and quality of international scientific co-publications, contributing to scientific progress and improving the reputation of Italian research globally.

Conclusions. The value of international scientific co-publications grew by an average of 44.85% between 2018 and 2023 in Italian regions. Looking at the data from the Italian macro-regions, we can see a significant distinction between Central, Northern, and Southern Italy. The Center leads the Italian macro-regions with an average value of 204.87 in 2023, followed by the North with 194.73 and the South with 130.54. The value of international scientific co-publications has grown significantly in the southern regions between 2018 and 2023, by an amount equal to 52.41%. However, the degree of internationalization of research is still low in the southern regions compared to the central-northern regions. It is noteworthy that the leading macro-region in international scientific collaborations is Central Italy and not the North. This condition means that universities and research centers in Central Italy have developed a capacity for international collaboration even higher than that of the wealthy northern regions, which generally host many southern and international students. To increase the value of international scientific co-publications, it is necessary to modify the engagement rules for academic and research personnel, imposing a certain number of international publications in selection processes.

Declarations

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Appendix

